

THE PROVISION OF INFORMATION ON SITES AND THEIR DESIGN

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Annotation: this article is written in online journalism about the appearance, structure of sites and the provision of information on them.

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Among the sites operating on the basis of the requirements of online journalism, first of all, are traditional media sites. All of them are engaged in the transfer of journalistic materials available on their site to appearance, and as a result, it is the political views that are published in the traditional way that reflect the views on the website. The local media, like the same one, publishes information on the website related to a specific area. It also implies that it instantly acquires global significance. Some websites in the US makes exchange of information in mutual publications by establishing partnerships with local radio television and press publications. This makes it possible for the data to be tracked in two ways, in a traditional and remote manner, but in any case, the original material transfer is the aspiration of all the media, for which, as a result of their cooperation, the audience reflected in the print media is counted from the participating significant aspects. The activity of newspaper TV and radio on the internet gives rise to a process of convergence. Both from the point of view of activity and from the point of view of content, this in its own way implies the conduct of two or more types of media activities in a mutually harmonious way. It is also worth recognizing that information delivery specialists have appeared. They are called journalist rugzak. This term, in turn, arose in such journalists due to the presence in the rug of equipment for obtaining information from the naturally desired form of audio photo. The preparation of an article for such journalists can also convey to other means, taking both the video and audio of the available information. Of course, in order to achieve success, such journalists must have the skills to be able to prepare material for various media. In the future, it will not be a mistake to say the requirement for all journalists. Another direction for the online journalist environment may be the creation of small publications specializing on several topics within a website as the activities of specialized publications also end. This specialization can be defined according to geographic indications or based on the subject. They, in turn, provide an opportunity to deeply cover the topic, as they are in a narrow topic, and at the same time

provide an opportunity to collect various media around it. One of the more important manifestations is these, as well as news aggregators. Speaking of journalistic websites and their types, you will see that the websites you follow are evaluated by the sites that are functioning effectively. This will help to know what requirements must be met in order to succeed in running sites in the future, to study the aspects of the structure of the site and the aspects that must be paid attention to for its updating, and to know in what way online uses the achievements of journalism on websites. When studying sites, put the following questions in front of you. Who are the organizers of the site, what is its content, is the information reliable, how often information is updated, what general idea the site has lost in you, answering these questions will allow you not only to correctly evaluate it, but also to determine whether it is actually a media site. It is important to know the content and purpose of the information contained in it in order to find out whether it was organized by the editorial board of the media political party or simply by amateurs to study its natural spirit about us, which exists on each site. What its content consists of journalism it is important that it always raises topics of social importance pointer. The inclusion of web pages aimed at them in the media will be a weapon of propaganda, and not the media, even those websites that are being promoted by organizations that remain incorrect. Therefore, it is necessary to be attentive as a journalist. Based on the content of the site, it is also said that it is not bad in the mass creed, then for example specialized publications on a narrow topic information corrects the width of the scope of topics in them also in one way or another can not be a clear indicator. To do this, it is necessary to pay attention to the next indication that is presented here. Is the data reliable it is not easy to answer the question of course you have it represents the opposite of course in every editorial it is for this reason that the musahhah operates. You will have the motivation to make sure. How quickly information is updated. Journalism it means striving for constant news so that the media site is also characterized by regular updates. Traditional publications and television sites are usually updated once a day after the publication of their main appearance or after the release of the holder but if there is regularity it is considered a press display of the media site. It is not difficult to determine what General vision you have in one vision. Usually the location of the procedures on the media sites makes sense. Of course, in terms of visibility, traditional media sites repeat the style of their region. When sorting materials as well, each individual tool has its own this method moves directly to the website.

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